

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Job stress and job involvement of criminology interns of Cagayan state University and its relationship to their OJT performance

Oliver G. Ferrer*

Faculty of College of Criminal Justice Education, Cagayan State University, Maura, Aparri, Cagayan, Philippines

Key words: Job stress, Job involvement, On-the-job training performance, Criminology interns

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.12692/jbes/27.5.1-11>

[Published: November 03, 2025]

ABSTRACT

In contemporary work environments, job-related stress has become an inevitable concern due to increasing professional demands and expectations. Individuals often experience stress when these demands exceed their capabilities, potentially influencing their job involvement and performance. This study examined the relationship between job stress and job involvement among Criminology interns of Cagayan State University during the Academic Year 2023–2024. Employing a descriptive research design and a questionnaire-checklist, data were collected from 297 interns across multiple campuses. Findings revealed common stressors such as workload management and ethical dilemmas, with noticeable variations in emotional engagement and job satisfaction. Despite these stressors, interns demonstrated high levels of job involvement characterized by task commitment, engagement, and a strong sense of belonging. Campus affiliation significantly affected both job stress and job involvement, underscoring the need for synchronized implementation of internship programs university-wide. Moreover, the study found no direct relationship between on-the-job training performance and licensure examination outcomes. The interns recommended interventions such as orientation, enhanced supervision, practical exposure, and stress management seminars. The study highlights the importance of continuous orientation, mentorship, and stress management programs to sustain and enhance the professional development and performance of criminology interns.

*Corresponding Author: Oliver G. Ferrer ✉ vermhieferrer0212@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

It is common for people to experience work-related stress when they face demands and pressures that surpass their abilities and knowledge. This stress can occur in various work situations, but it is often worsened when employees feel unsupported by their supervisors and colleagues, or when they have little control over the work process. However, it is important to distinguish between stress and challenges, as stress can lead to severe health issues and should not be used to excuse bad management practices.

In a contemporary work environment, pressure is unavoidable due to the nature of the job. If the pressure is perceived as acceptable, it can even keep workers motivated and alert, allowing them to perform their duties effectively. However, when that pressure becomes excessive and unmanageable, it leads to stress, which can damage both the employee's health and the business's performance.

According to CMO no. 5 Series of 2018 which deals with Policies, Standards and Guidelines for Bachelor of Science in Criminology Program, a Criminology Interns must undergo a two semester, 540 hours Practicum 1 and 2 / Community Immersion with 6 credit units is a requirements where in the students are assigned in different areas of the community. The Unique feature of the program is the students' contribution to "police visibility". This serves as the main role of the Criminology interns of Cagayan State University during their internship program. Aside from their contributions to police visibility, the interns were also assigned in other law enforcement agencies such as Bureau of Fire Protection, Bureau of Jail Management and Penology, Philippine Coast guard and the likes which will mold them into a well-rounded future law enforcer.

Law Enforcement agencies plays vital role among Criminology Interns as they can impart the actual work experiences that will mold a well-rounded future law enforcers but on the other hand Cagayan State University is not the only institution offering

Criminology Program who sends their interns in different law enforcement agencies, as a result, the delivery of actual work experiences and learnings might be affected because of population of the interns coming from different institutions. This matter might bring job stress and affect the job involvement of the students during their internship program.

Criminology interns at Cagayan State University can experience significant impacts on their learning experience and future career trajectories due to job stress and job involvement. Job stress can be defined as the emotional or physical strain that occurs when the demands of a job exceed an individual's ability to cope. For criminology interns, this stress can arise from various factors, including the nature of their work, exposure to challenging situations, or pressure to perform efficiently in a high-stakes environment. Job involvement, on the other hand, refers to the degree to which individuals identify themselves with their job, find meaning and satisfaction from their work. For criminology interns, high job involvement may indicate a strong passion for their field of study and a deep commitment to the tasks and responsibilities assigned during their internship.

It is essential to understand the dynamics of job stress and job involvement among criminology interns at Cagayan State University to assess their overall well-being, performance, and potential career success. This understanding can shed light on the factors that contribute to their stress levels, their engagement with the internship, and ways to enhance their learning experience for better professional development. This matter captures the interest of the researchers of this study to find out the job stress and job involvement of criminology interns of Cagayan State University in their respective workplace to contribute in more dynamic way of imparting knowledge and skills among students through effective and efficient actual job engagements.

This study aims to determine and assess the Job Stress and Job Involvement of Criminology Interns

of Cagayan State University for the Academic Year 2023-2024 and its relationship to their OJT Performance. It focuses on describing the demographic profile of the participants, assessing the extent of job stress and level of job involvement in their respective assignments, and evaluating their OJT performance for the first semester of the academic year. The study further explores whether significant differences exist in job stress and job involvement when grouped according to demographic profiles, and examines the relationship between job stress, job involvement, and OJT performance. It also investigates the correlation between the interns' OJT performance and their Institutional Board Examination ratings, while gathering their suggested measures to enhance the overall internship program.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research design

This study used descriptive correlational research design. This design is a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. It is also a technique with adequate interpretation of data derived from the survey which utilize a questionnaire. This method will also measure the relationship in Job Stress and Job involvement of Criminology Interns of Cagayan State University.

Respondents of the study

The respondents of this study are the fourth year criminology interns of Cagayan State University Aparri, Gonzaga, Piat, and Sanchez Mira campuses officially enrolled for the academic year 2023-2024. Total Enumeration will be used among all campuses having their Internship program. The responses of the Criminology Interns were the core matter in the realization of the study (Table 1).

Table 1. Respondents of the study

Camus	Frequency	Percentage
Aparri	117	39.39%
Gonzaga	60	20.20%
Piat	74	24.91%
Sanchez Mira	46	15.48%
Total	297	100%

Data gathering instrument

Questionnaire

Adapted Questionnaire from the study of (Edem *et al.*, 2022) with few modifications was used as main data gathering tool. It consist of three parts: Profile of the participants, their assessments on Job Stress and their job involvement during On-the-job training in their place of assignment.

Analysis of data

In analyzing the data, various statistical tools were employed to address the objectives of the study. Frequency and percentage were used to describe the profile variables of the participants. The assessment of job stress and the perception of job involvement during the on-the-job training were analyzed using the weighted mean based on a five-point Likert scale.

Frequency and percentage distribution were also utilized to evaluate the On-the-Job Training (OJT) performance of the Criminology Interns. To determine significant differences in the assessment of job stress when grouped according to profile variables, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed, while the Kruskal-Wallis test was used to identify significant differences in job involvement perceptions across profile groups. The relationship between job stress, job involvement, and OJT performance was examined using Spearman's Rho correlation, whereas the relationship between OJT performance and Institutional Board Examination ratings was analyzed through Pearson correlation. Finally, frequency and rank distribution were applied to identify the measures suggested by participants for improving the internship program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the analysis of the data gathered through the research instruments imposed, the following were the findings:

Part I. Respondents' assessment on the job stress in their place of assignment as criminology interns

Table 2 presents the assessment of the criminology interns on Job stress in their workplace using a five-point Likert scale.

Table 2. Mean distribution of the participants' assessment on the job stress in their place of assignment

Job stress	Mean	DR
1. Managing the emotional toll of engaging with real-life criminal cases gave me stress during internship program.	3.2	EAD
2. Balancing the demands of caseloads and tight deadlines has created high levels of job stress	3.5	A
3. The pressure to apply theoretical knowledge in practical scenarios, coupled with the responsibility of contributing to criminal investigations are stressful to me	3.2	EAD
4. Dealing with the unpredictability and intensity of criminal situations has presented a unique set of challenges, contributing to stress on my part as Criminology Intern.	3.3	EAD
5. Navigating the ethical dilemmas and moral complexities inherent in criminological work has added a layer of stress for me as interns, requiring constant reflection and decision-making.	3.2	EAD
6. Coping with the gravity of criminal cases, including exposure to violence, victims' stories, and the criminal justice system's shortcomings, has been emotionally taxing for me as criminology intern.	3.2	EAD
7. The necessity to establish rapport and communicate effectively with diverse stakeholders, including law enforcement, victims, and offenders, has been a stressor for me as criminology intern.	3.18	EAD
8. Juggling multiple tasks, such as conducting interviews, analyzing evidence, and preparing reports, has created time and workload pressures for interns in criminology	3.4	A
9. My job is very complicated, and there is a heavy workload	3	EAD
10. Worry about personal safety at job	3.2	EAD
11. I often do overtime in my job	2.98	EAD
12. Great responsibility, afraid of accountability	3	EAD
13. I do not know much about my job	2.6	EAD
14. My job has not been clearly explained and explained	2.6	EAD
15. Sometimes I am assigned to different positions at the same time	3.3	EAD
16. Conflict or unhappiness with colleagues	2.7	EAD
17. Feel isolated at the job	2.6	EAD
18. Lack of support from leadership	2.6	EAD
19. Leaders were unwilling or unable to help me with my job problems	2.6	EAD
20. The organization did not respond well to my performance	2.6	EAD
21. I am worried about my future career development	3.3	EAD
22. My rights are sometimes not protected	2.7	EAD

DR- Descriptive Rate; SA- Strongly Agree; A- Agree; EAD- Either Agree or Disagree; D- Disagree; SD- Strongly Disagree

It can be deduced from the table that the assessments of the respondents have a little variation in each variable. The respondents were either agree or disagree in all job stress items except for items number 2 and 8 in which they assessed it as agree. It is also noted that the overall mean of Job stress is 3.0 in which the respondents either agree or disagree.

The result reveals that the average scores generally revolve around the midpoint, indicating that participants typically have mixed feelings about the various aspects of job stress during their internship. Certain stressors, such as balancing the demands of caseloads and deadlines, and juggling multiple tasks, were more commonly acknowledged as sources of stress. The result runs parallel to the article of World

Health Organization (2022, November). Occupational health, which states that poor work design like juggling multiple tasks can cause work related stress among workers.

Part II. Respondents' job involvement during on-the-job training in their place of assignment as criminology interns

The table below displays the assessment of the criminology interns on job involvement in their workplace using a five-point Likert scale.

It is evident from the table that there is minimal variation in the assessments of the respondents for each variable. Majority of the respondents agree in all Job involvement items except for item number

11 in which they're either agree or disagree; and item number 13 which they assessed disagree. Further analysis also indicates that High levels of engagement, commitment to team success,

feedback utilization, meaningful work, enthusiasm, and a sense of belonging were among the highest mean scores which the respondents agreed upon (Table 3).

Table 3. Mean distribution of the participants' job involvement during on-the-job training

Job stress	Mean	DR
1. I collaborate with law enforcement officers to analyze crime data, identify patterns, and contribute to the development of crime prevention strategies within the community.	3.6	A
2. I assist in the preparation of comprehensive reports on criminal investigations, summarizing findings and recommendations for law enforcement agencies	3.5	A
3. I participate in field observations and accompanied professionals on crime scene visits, gaining hands-on experience in evidence collection and forensic procedures.	3.5	A
4. I contribute to the creation and implementation of community outreach programs aimed at raising awareness about crime prevention and promoting public safety.	3.7	A
5. I participate in ride-along with law enforcement officers to observe and understand real-world criminal justice practices	3.6	A
6. I engaged with community members through outreach programs, facilitating discussions on crime prevention, safety, and community policing	3.7	A
7. I participate in training sessions on investigative techniques, criminal profiling, and other relevant topics to enhance professional skills.	3.7	A
8. I assist in the preparation and delivery of training materials for law enforcement personnel	3.5	A
9. I establish and nurture professional relationships with mentors and colleagues, creating a valuable network within the criminal justice field.	3.7	A
10. My job is the most important part of my life	3.8	A
11. I do not feel emotionally involved in my job	3	EAD
12. I would feel guilty if I left my days job incomplete	3.7	A
13. I do not enjoy my job	2.4	D
14. I am highly engaged in my tasks and responsibilities	3.8	A
15. I am committed to the success of my team and actively collaborate to achieve our shared objectives.	3.9	A
16. I seek feedback on my performance and use it to continuously improve in my role	3.9	A
17. I find my work meaningful and am dedicated to making a positive impact through my contributions	4	A
18. I am enthusiastic about my job and find it personally rewarding	3.9	A
19. I feel a strong sense of belonging and connection to my team and organization	3.9	A

DR- Descriptive Rate; SA- Strongly Agree; A- Agree; EAD- Either Agree or Disagree; D- Disagree; SD- Strongly Disagree

However, while participants are highly engaged and committed to their roles, there's a notable discrepancy in terms of emotional involvement and enjoyment of their job. It is also further noted that 3.7 is the overall mean score of the Job involvement of criminology interns.

The findings complements with the content of a book of Organizational Behavior in Southern Africa, 2nd edition Job involvement, which states that those who are more involved with their job are more likely to experience challenges due to competing work and family demands.

Part III. Respondents' on-the-job training performance

The table below reflects the frequency and percentage distribution of the Criminology Interns of Cagayan State University according to their OJT performance.

The result reveals that 185 or 62.28 percent of the 297 Criminology Interns have an Outstanding performance; 98 or 32.99 percent performs *Very Satisfactory*, and 14 or 4.71 percent are Satisfactory performing. The finding implies that majority of the Criminology Interns of Cagayan State University performs Outstanding in their respective On-The-Job

Training agencies. The findings further indicates that the interns demonstrated high degree of excellence in different aspects of their On-The-Job Training .

The findings complements with the result of the study of (Suetos, 2023), On-the-job training program effectiveness and performance of BSIT students of CSU Gonzaga, in which Cagayan State University Students demonstrated excellent performance in various OJT aspects, including quality of work, job knowledge, and human relations (Table 4).

Table 4. Frequency and percentage distribution of the OJT performance of the participants

Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	185	62.28
Very satisfactory	98	32.99
Satisfactory	14	4.71
Fair	-	-
Poor	-	-
total	297	100

Part IV. Difference in the assessments of the participants in the job stress and job involvement in their place of assignment when group according to their profiles

Table 5 shows the result of the test of significant difference in the assessments of the participants' Job Stress when group according to profiles when

Table 5. Test of difference in the participants' job stress when group according to profiles

Profile	F-Test		Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Probability (P)	Alpha (A)			
Age	0.6	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Sex	0.33	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Civil status	0.74	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Campus	0.004	0.05	P < A	Ho is rejected	Significant

It shows that Sanchez Mira, Aparri, and Piat Campuses all belong to subset 1 and do not differ significantly from each other in Job Stress scores. On the other hand, Gonzaga Campus Belongs to Subset 2 with a mean Job Stress score of 3.33 and is significantly higher than those in Subset 1 (Table 6). The findings implies that Criminology Interns of CSU- Gonzaga has the highest Job Stress scores among others. It is also noted that their interns were being deployed in Gonzaga and Santa Teresita Law Enforcement Agencies.

grouped according to their profile using the Analysis of Variance F-test of the computer aided statistics at level of significance, alpha 0.05.

For the profile variable on age, sex and marital status, the computed F-probability (P) of 0.6, 0.33, and 0.74, respectively are greater than the given level of significance alpha (A) at 0.05.

This led to the acceptance of the null hypothesis; hence, the job stress of the respondents does not influenced by their age, sex, and marital status. On the other hand, the respondents' campus affiliation significantly cause a difference in the respondents' job stress. This is shown in the computed F-probability (P) of 0.004 which is less than the given level of significance alpha (A) at 0.05.

The findings contradict with the study of Satria *et al.* (2020) which states that age influences the level of stress while on the other hand, sex and marital status have no effect on the stress level.

The table below presents the Tukey test result of the job stress scores of the participants according to their campus affiliations.

Part V. Difference in the assessments of the participants in the job involvement in their place of assignment when group according to their profiles

Table below shows the result of the test of significant difference in the assessments of the participants' Job Involvement when grouped according to their profile using the Kruskal-Wallis of the computer aided statistics at level of significance, alpha 0.05. For the profile variables of age, sex, and marital status, the computed probabilities (P) of 0.107, 0.316, and 0.45,

respectively, are greater than the given alpha of 0.05. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, indicating that job involvement is not influenced by age, sex, and marital status.

Table 6. Tukey test of the Job Stress of the participants according to campus affiliations

Campus	N	Subset for Alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Sanchez Mira	46	2.8498	
Aparri	117	2.9437	
Piat	74	2.9582	
Gonzaga	60		3.3303

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

However, the participants' campus affiliation does significantly influence job involvement.

This is indicated by the computed probability (P) of 0.001, which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. This further implies that campuses affects the views and emotion of the interns to be job involved in their workplace.

The findings run parallel with the result of the study of (Marie *et al.*, 2009) which states that Job involvement also had a positive association with emotional exhaustion (Table 7).

Table 7. Test of difference in the participants' job involvement when group according to profiles

Profile	Kruskal-Wallis		Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Probability (P)	Alpha (A)			
Age	0.107	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Sex	0.316	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Marital status	0.45	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Non-significant
Campus	0.001	0.05	P < A	Ho is rejected	Significant

Table 8. Result of the test of significant relationship between the participants' job stress, job involvement and their OJT performance

Variables		Spearman's Rho		Analysis	Decision	Remarks
		Probability (P)	Alpha (A)			
OJT performance	Job stress	0.189	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Not significant
OJT performance	Job involvement	0.102	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Not significant
Job stress	Job involvement	0.000	0.05	P < A	Ho is rejected	Significant

Part VI. Correlation between the participants' job stress, job involvement and their OJT performance

Table 8 shows the result of the test of significant relationship between the Participants' Job stress, Job Involvement and their OJT Performance using the Spearman's Rho correlation of the computer aided statistics at level of significance, alpha 0.05.

The computed probabilities (P) of 0.189 and 0.102 for Job stress and Job Involvement correlated to OJT Performance of the participants is greater than the given level of significance alpha (A) at 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This result implies no significant relationship between the OJT performance correlated to job

stress and job involvement of the Criminology Interns at Cagayan State University.

On the other hand, the computed probability of 0.000 for Job stress when correlated to Job involvement is less than the given level of significance alpha (A) at 0.05, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This implies a significant relationship between the job stress and job involvement of the Criminology Interns at Cagayan State University.

The result contradicts with the study of (Edem *et al.*, 2022) which states that the job stress experienced by interns negatively predicts job involvement.

Table 9. Result of the test of significant relationship between the participants’ OJT Performances and their institutional board exam ratings

Variables	Pearson r		Analysis	Decision	Remarks
	Probability (P)	Alpha (A)			
OJT performance board exam rating	0.829	0.05	P > A	Ho is accepted	Not significant

Table 10. Frequency and rank distribution of the suggested measures to improve the internship programs

Measures	Frequency	Rank
1. Orientation among Criminology interns before deployment to different agencies ensuring that students understand the skills and knowledge they are expected to gain per Law enforcement agencies they are deployed.	213	1
2. Stress management seminar to be conducted by the institution to address the job stress of interns in their on-the-job training	174	4
3. Inclusion of mentorship programs that pair students with experienced professionals in the field, providing guidance, support, and valuable insights throughout the internship.	142	7
4. Design rotational internship programs among all available law enforcement agencies near the institution that expose students to various aspects of criminology, including law enforcement, criminal justice, corrections, and community-based initiatives.	149	5
5. Application of theoretical knowledge gained in the classroom to real-world scenarios, allowing students to bridge the gap between academic concepts and practical skills through hands-on work activities per Law enforcement agencies.	143	6
6. Regular supervision and constructive feedback from OJT Coordinator and experienced professionals to help them understand their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.	177	3
7. Providing interns with opportunities by the agencies to engage in the actual job per agencies for them to learn things by doing it.	178	2

Part VII. Correlation between the participants’ OJT performances and their institutional board exam ratings

Table 9 shows the result of the test of significant relationship between the Participants’ OJT Performances and their Institutional Board Exam Ratings using the Pearson Correlation of the computer aided statistics at level of significance, alpha 0.05.

The computed probability (P) of 0.829 for the OJT performance and Board Exam Rating of the participants is higher than the given level of significance alpha (A) at 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This result implies no significant relationship between OJT performance of the Criminology Interns at Cagayan State University and their and Board Exam Result.

The result opposes the study of (Beverly *et al.*, 2025) which states that internships significantly affects the licensure examination performances.

Part VIII. Participants’ suggested measures to improve their internship programs

Table 10 displays the result of the frequency and rank distribution of the suggested measures to improve the internship programs.

It can be deduced from the table that orientation among criminology interns before deployment to different agencies rank as first; providing interns with opportunities to engage in the actual job rank as second; regular supervision and constructive feedback rank as third; stress management seminar rank as fourth; designing rotational internship programs rank as sixth; and Inclusion of mentorship programs rank as the least among the suggested measures.

The result implies that there is a clear preference for approaches that offer guidance through orientation, hands-on practice, and supportive supervision. It also emphasizes the significance of stress management for interns in criminology programs.

CONCLUSION

This study determined and assessed the Job Stress and Job involvement of Criminology Interns of Cagayan State University for the Academic Year 2023-2024 and its relationship to their OJT Performance. The examination of job stress among criminology interns reveals a consensus on certain stress factors such as workload management and ethical dilemmas, with variations in emotional involvement and job enjoyment. There is consistent high job involvement among interns, characterized by significant engagement, task commitment, and a strong sense of belonging. This positive outlook is mirrored in their exceptional performance during on-the-job training (OJT), with the majority demonstrating outstanding performance.

The campus affiliation profile has a notable effect on both aspects of job stress or job involvement. On-the-job training (OJT) performance found no relation with the levels of job stress and job involvement. However, job stress and job involvement shows relationship, suggesting that the job stress experienced by interns can influence their level of job involvement, or vice versa. While OJT performances of the Criminology Interns when correlated to their Institutional Board Exam Result found out no relations. Moreover, interns have proposed various measures to enhance their internship experience, prioritizing orientation, practical engagement, supervision, and stress management seminars.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study on the Job Stress and Job Involvement of Criminology Interns of Cagayan State University and Its Relationship to their OJT Performance, the researcher offers the following recommendations:

1. The college is encouraged to implement orientation for criminology interns before deployment to different agencies. This ensures that the students understand the skills and knowledge expected by law enforcement agencies.
2. The partner agencies is advised to provide interns with opportunities to engage in the actual job

performance like traffic management engagements, actual fire suppressions, jail management procedures and water survival activities for them to learn things by doing it and for them to feel emotional involvement and enjoyment of their job.

3. Regular supervision and constructive feedback from OJT Coordinators and experienced professionals to help the interns understand their strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement.
4. Campus affiliation has a notable effect on both aspects of Job stress and Job involvement of the Criminology Interns, hence, University wide synchronization of programs and activities with regards to Criminology internship program is encouraged addressing the differences or gaps on Job Stress and Job involvement per campus.
5. Job stress and Job involvement of the Criminology Interns have a significant relationships, therefore, Regular Job stress and Job involvement orientation and seminars like stress management workshops and supervision and mentorship programs are advised to be conducted by the college and partner agencies to address job stress levels and further improve job involvement of Criminology Interns.
6. It is recommended that the College of Criminal Justice Education continue to enhance and institutionalize its internship framework by integrating comprehensive pre-deployment orientations, regular stress management seminars, and synchronized internship standards across all campuses. These measures should be sustained and periodically evaluated to ensure alignment with AACUP's Key Area on Instructions and Support to Students, thereby promoting continuous quality improvement of the delivery of the program.

REFERENCES

- Azila-Gbettor EM, Atsu E, Quarshie ANK.** 2022. Job stress and job involvement among tertiary interns: The buffering role of perceived coworker support. *Heliyon* **8**(9).

- Bennett NJ, Finkbeiner EM, Ban NC, Belhabib D, Jupiter SD, Kittinger JN, Christie P.** 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic, small-scale fisheries and coastal fishing communities. *Coastal Management* **48**(4), 336–347.
- Dionio BB, Dagpin ARR, Cabillas AJQB, Edullantes JRT, Baluyos GR.** 2025. Predictors of graduates' performance in the licensure examination for teachers (LET). *EduLine: Journal of Education and Learning Innovation* **5**(1), 79–103.
- Eccles JS, Wigfield A.** 2002. Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology* **53**(1), 109–132.
- Giannakis E, Hadjioannou L, Jimenez C, Papageorgiou M, Karonias A, Petrou A.** 2020. Economic consequences of coronavirus disease (COVID-19) on fisheries in the eastern Mediterranean (Cyprus). *Sustainability* **12**(22), 9406.
- Gogua I.** 2020. Juvenile delinquency—causes, prevention, and the ways of rehabilitation.
- Griffin ML, Hogan NL, Lambert EG, Tucker-Gail KA, Baker DN.** 2010. Job involvement, job stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment and the burnout of correctional staff. *Criminal Justice and Behavior* **37**(2), 239–255.
- Lambert EG, Hogan NL, Barton SM, Elechi OO.** 2009. The impact of job stress, job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment on correctional staff support for rehabilitation and punishment. *Criminal Justice Studies* **22**(2), 109–122.
- Lambert EG, Qureshi H, Frank J, Klahm C, Smith B.** 2018. Job stress, job involvement, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment and their associations with job burnout among Indian police officers: a research note. *Journal of Police and Criminal Psychology* **33**, 85–99.
- Leone PE, Christle CA, Nelson CM, Skiba R, Frey A, Jolivette K.** 2003. School failure, race, and disability: promoting positive outcomes, decreasing vulnerability for involvement with the juvenile delinquency system. *EDJJ: The National Center on Education, Disability, and Juvenile Justice*, 1–46.
- Li JJ.** 2018. A study on university teachers' job stress—from the aspect of job involvement. *Journal of Interdisciplinary Mathematics* **21**(2), 341–349.
- Mensah C, Azila-Gbettor EM, Appietu ME, Agbodza JS.** 2021. Internship work-related stress: a comparative study between hospitality and marketing students. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Education* **33**(1), 29–42.
- National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH).** 2022. Stress at work. Retrieved November 7, 2022, from <https://www.cdc.gov/niosh/docs/99-101/default.html#:~:text=done%20about%20it,-,What%20Is%20Job%20Stress%3F,poor%20health%20and%20even%20injury>
- Robbins SP.** 2009. Organisational behaviour in Southern Africa. Pearson South Africa.
- Satria RMA, Harlinisari R, Prestiono I, Kusumo AD, Purnomo W.** 2020. The relation of depression, anxiety and stress with demographic profile of nurses. *EurAsian Journal of BioSciences* **14**(2), 3537–3542.
- Study.Com.** 2022. What is job involvement?—definition & scale. Retrieved November 7, 2022, from <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-job-involvement-definition-scale-quiz.html>
- Suetos ER.** 2023. On-the-job training program effectiveness and performance of BSIT students of CSU Gonzaga. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Education* **9**(2), 17–29.

Wang X, Han Y, Chai R, Chai R. 2021. [Retracted] Stressors of nursing interns and their influencing factors: a cross-sectional study. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering* **2021**(1), 3561628.

World Health Organization. 2022. Occupational health: stress at the workplace. <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/occupational-health-stress-at-the-workplace>

Zeinolabedini M, Heidarnia A, Shakerinejad G, Motlagh ME, Zeidi IM. 2023. Perceptions and experiences of health care workers and superiors about workplace stress: a conceptual model for promoting mental health in the workplace. *Authorea Preprints*.